

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF TEMPERATURE AND FREQUENCY EFFECTS
ON LOW-CYCLE FATIGUE STRENGTH OF GLASS-MAT FRP

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ABSTRACT

Statistical analysis of low-cycle fatigue life data of glass-mat FRP at low frequencies ranging approximately 0.003 to 0.1 Hz was performed based on the log-normal distribution. In the stress-median life diagram, it was found that one regression line is obtained for low and intermediate temperature levels, while the median life data at higher temperature than the heat distortion temperature of the resin fit well to another regression line with approximately the same slope located at the lower stress level by 12 %. It is also said that frequency effects at each testing temperature are comprehended when the stress level in low-cycle fatigue tests is standardized by the tensile strength under the associate test conditions. Moreover, monitoring the strain response during fatigue tests and examining the ratio of the plastic strain to the total one, the relation between such strain ratio and the S-N diagram is discussed.

INTRODUCTION

It is well-known that the fatigue behavior of glass-fiber reinforced plastics (GFRP) is mainly dependent upon the loading rate or frequency and the environmental temperature. There are, however, few reports concerning frequency effects of GFRP under different temperature environments at considerably low frequencies ranging less than approximately 0.1 Hz to prevent any significant hysteric heating.^{1,2} This situation may be found in such as the case where an FRP plant is in service outside under cyclic and slow change in its fluid quantity.

In the present paper, low-cycle tensile fatigue tests for glass-mat FRP were conducted at low (-20°C), intermediate (20°C) and high (100°C) temperatures, where the heat distortion temperature of the resin used here is about 70°C. In each test, the loading stress rate was also selected by ranging approximately 0.003 to 0.1 Hz in frequency. In order to examine the effects of temperature and loading frequency on the fatigue life, life data with considerably high scatter were analyzed by a statistical method based on the log-normal distribution. A stress-median life diagram was adopted to evaluate the low-cycle fatigue strength. In another fatigue test using a strain-gage method, the relation between the S-N diagram and the strain at the fatigue failure was made clear.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The test specimen used in this investigation is a tabbed straight-sided one as shown in Fig. 1, where tabs were molded in a metal die at the same time when the laminates were molded. It is fabricated by several layers of chopped strand glass-mat with unsaturated polyester resin whose heat distortion temperature is about 70°C. Environmental temperatures were controlled at -20, 20 and 100°C. The tensile

fatigue test was run at low frequencies of approximately 0.1, 0.02 and 0.003 Hz corresponding to loading stress rates of 35, 10 and 1 MPa/s, respectively. In these cases, stress levels were set at 80-90 % for -20 and 20°C, and at 68-77 % for 100°C, respectively. The sample size of fatigue test specimen under each test condition was more than 14 considering statistical analysis of life data.

Fig. 1 Specimen geometry (dimensions in mm)

First, static tests of the same test specimens as used in the fatigue test were conducted for tension mode with an Instron type testing machine. Temperature levels were 3 levels of -20, 20 and 100°C. A thermostatic chamber was used at the temperature controlled tests. Tests were run at loading stress rates of 35, 10 and 1 MPa/s. Among them, the test case at 100°C with the loading stress rate of 35 MPa/s could not be realized not only in the fatigue test but also in the static test for lack of the follow-up capacity of testing machine.

Next, the tension-tension low-cycle fatigue tests were performed with the same testing machine as used in the static tests under the same test condition of both the temperature and the loading stress rate as in the static test. In the fatigue test, stress levels were determined so that test specimens might fail until 200 to 300 cycles. Thus stress levels defined as the ratio of stress amplitude to the static tensile strength were 80, 85 and 90 % for temperature levels of -20 and 20°C, and 68, 72 and 77 % for 100°C, respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Data analysis of fatigue life based on log-normal distribution

First, the change in tensile strengths with the testing temperature and the loading stress rate is shown in Table 1. Each value is the mean. The variation of coefficient for these tensile strengths was less than 10 %.

Secondly, the S-N diagrams obtained from low-cycle fatigue tests are given in Figs. 2(a)-(c). It is found that the scatter of life data is considerably high in spite of the fact that that of static tensile strength was comparatively low. Therefore, these life data will be treated from the statistical viewpoint. If it is assumed that they follow the log-normal distribution, an example of the plots of the probability of failure is illustrated in Fig. 3. They are calculated by the mean ranking method. As the results of data analysis, the median life, the mean, the standard deviation and the coefficient of variation are given in Table 2 with sample sizes. It is found that the scatter of life data is almost lower for lower stress level, lower loading rate and lower temperature.

Table 1 Static tensile strength

Temp. (°C)	Stress Rate (MPa/s)		
	1.0	10.0	35.0
-20	208	220	225
20	199	210	220
100	143	158	-

2. Frequency effects on fatigue life

In order to examine the frequency effects on the fatigue life, median life data with upper and lower limits are illustrated in Figs. 4(a)-(c) with the ordinate of cycles to failure and the abscissa of frequency corresponding to the loading stress rate tested under each condition. The frequency is the inverse of twice the stress amplitude divided by the stress rate. From these results, it can be said that the number of cycles to failure inclines to decrease with the increase of frequency.

This is due to the reason why the plastic strain at the 1st cycle will increase with the increase of frequency judging from the strain responses in another experiment described later.

Fig. 2(a) S-N diagram (Temp. = -20°C)

Fig. 2(b) S-N diagram (Temp. = 20°C)

Fig. 2(c) S-N diagram (Temp. = 100°C)

Fig. 3 An example of probability of failure for failure cycles N_f

3. Evaluation of fatigue strength

The stress-median life diagram is adopted to evaluate the low-cycle fatigue strength under several test conditions. Then the ordinate is the stress level S' which is defined as the ratio of the stress amplitude to the tensile strength at the associate temperature and at loading stress rate of 10 MPa/s. On the other hand, for the abscissa, the median life N_m is plotted in log-scale. Thus, Fig. 5 has been obtained. In the figure, two regression lines are given by the least

Table 2 Results of statistical analysis based on log-normal distribution

Temp. °C	Stress Rate MPa/s	Stress Level %	Sample Size	Median Life	Mean	Standard Deviation	C.V. %
-20	1	90	17	10.5	1.02	0.56	54.7
		85	16	23.1	1.36	0.54	39.6
		80	14	44.6	1.65	0.45	27.1
	10	90	15	8.7	0.94	0.42	44.6
		85	19	12.9	1.11	0.61	55.4
		80	15	42.3	1.63	0.45	27.0
	35	90	16	8.2	0.91	0.40	44.2
		85	14	16.1	1.21	0.30	25.1
		80	15	38.3	1.58	0.34	21.9
20	1	90	17	14.0	1.15	0.48	41.5
		85	15	24.3	1.39	0.69	49.5
		80	16	39.4	1.60	0.68	42.5
	10	90	15	8.4	0.92	0.42	44.8
		85	15	18.8	1.27	0.64	50.1
		80	17	38.2	1.58	0.43	27.3
	35	90	16	5.8	0.76	0.36	48.5
		85	15	8.3	0.92	0.43	46.9
		80	15	23.5	1.37	0.43	30.9
100	1	77	15	18.2	1.26	0.46	36.7
		72	15	31.0	1.49	0.43	29.1
		68	14	66.4	1.82	0.34	18.9
	10	77	16	9.2	0.96	0.68	70.8
		72	16	17.0	1.23	0.54	44.2
		68	16	27.2	1.44	0.59	41.2

Fig. 4(a) Frequency effects on fatigue life (Temp. = -20 °C)

Fig. 4(b) Frequency effects on fatigue life (Temp. = 20 °C)

square method, where the approximate equation is $S' = -A \log N_m + B$. Two parameters A and B are listed in Table 3. From these data, it is found that the former regression line intersects at about 100 % of stress level, while the latter fits well to another regression line with approximately the same slope located at the lower stress level by 12 %. This result suggests that the temperature effect on the low-cycle fatigue strength of glass-mat FRP at the high temperature is more remarkable than that at low and intermediate temperatures in comparison with the case of static strength. From the observation of failed test specimens, at -20 and 20°C, all most of specimens failed in fiber breakage mode, but at 100°C, the fiber pull-out took place in the specimens. Thus, it can be said that the strength reduction due to fiber pull-out is more remarkable in the fatigue test than in the static test. It is also found that the frequency effect is comprehended when the stress level is standardized as mentioned before.

4. Strain response and fatigue failure

In the low-cycle fatigue test, the strain response was monitored by a desk-top computer in the same manner as used in the Ref. (3), where we utilized a test specimen having a plastic-strain gage put between layers at the same time when the laminate was molded.

Now, the strain ratio is defined as that of the plastic strain to the total one at each repeated cycle. According to the

Fig. 6 Relation between ϵ_f^f and S'

Fig. 4(c) Frequency effects on fatigue life (Temp. = 100°C)

Fig. 5 Stress-median life diagram

Table 3 Values of parameters A and B

Temp. (°C)	A	B
-20, 20	16.66	105.4
100	17.85	93.4

Fig. 7 Relation between ϵ_r^f and $N_f - 1$

Fig. 8 Relation between S-N diagram and ϵ_r^f

experimental results, the ratio ϵ_r increases approximately linearly with the logarithm of the repeated cycle. Let the notation be ϵ_r^f as the ratio at one cycle before the cycle N_f at which the fatigue failure of specimens occurs.

Fig. 6 shows the relation between ϵ_r^f and stress level S' for -20 and 20°C , where there are no data for 100°C since the strain gage method could not be used at such high temperature. Similarly, the relation of ϵ_r^f versus $N_f - 1$ can be given as shown in Fig. 7. Both of them are approximately expressed by linear lines obtained using the least square method. Thus, the relation between S' and $N_f - 1$ which is corresponding to the S-N curve is given on a semi-log diagram of Fig. 8. Consequently, the ratio of the plastic strain to the total strain at the n -th cycle can be regarded as a kind of failure criterion.

CONCLUSION

Results of statistical analysis based on the log-normal distribution for low-cycle fatigue life data of glass-mat FRP can be summarized as follows;

1) The scatter of low-cycle fatigue life data is considerably high, while the coefficients of variation of static strength are within 10%.

2) The number of cycles to failure inclines to decrease with the increase of frequency.

3) Two regression lines are given on the stress-median life diagram. One is for -20 and 20°C and the other is for 100°C . It can be said that the strength reduction due to fiber pull-out is more remarkable in the fatigue test than in the static test.

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